

Influence of Crystal Fiber Inhomogeneity on the Energy Resolution of a Sampling Electromagnetic Calorimeter

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Abstract—Sampling electromagnetic calorimeters (ECALs) are widely used in high-energy physics experiments thanks to their ability to efficiently measure electromagnetic particles' energy over a broad dynamic range while maintaining good energy resolution. These detectors alternate passive layers made of dense absorber materials, with active layers, like scintillators.

Scintillating materials, such as inorganic garnets, are promising candidates for high-luminosity environments like the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) due to their high radiation hardness, ensuring longer operational lifetimes without compromising performance. However, fluctuations in light yield (LY) can lead to a degradation in energy resolution (E_R).

One concept of sampling calorimeter is the so called spaghetti calorimeter (SpaCaL), it relies on optimal scintillating fiber placement inserted in heavy absorber. Hence addressing possible LY variations is critical to guarantee that the detector meets the stringent requirements of future high-luminosity runs at the LHC. To maintain optimal ECAL performance, providing feedback to scintillator producers on the acceptable limits of LY variation is essential.

For this purpose, a W-GAGG SpaCal was modeled using Monte Carlo methods. Electrons with energies ranging from 1 to 100 GeV were simulated through the SpaCal to study E_R . We introduced artificial longitudinal variations of LY along the GAGG fibers with fixed values across a range of conditions to evaluate their impact on our modeled detector's performance.

Our results indicate that, to preserve the E_R and maintain an acceptable constant term $c = 1\%$, the longitudinal variation of LY should not exceed $2\%/cm$. Additionally, we found the optimal fiber configuration to minimize performance degradation from LY fluctuations by testing different end orientations and placements relative to the reflector in both SpaCal sections.

Index Terms—High energy physics (HEP), Calorimetry, Monte Carlo Simulation, Geant4, Advanced scintillation materials

I. INTRODUCTION

Electromagnetic calorimeter (ECAL) are used in high-energy physics (HEP) experiments to precisely measure the energy, position, and the timing of electrons, positrons, and photons.

The spaghetti calorimeter also known as SpaCal, [1] [2], shown in Figure 1, is a type of sampling ECAL where

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Manuscript received MM DD, YYYY; revised MM DD, YYYY.

scintillating fibers are embedded within a dense absorber. The main purpose of the absorber is to induce electromagnetic showers, while the one of the scintillators is to sample the shower and convert the deposited energy into optical signal that is then fed to photodetectors on both ends of the detector.

A key advantage of this design is its 15 mm granularity [5], which enhances spatial resolution for measuring shower development. While this does not directly control shower containment, it improves the ability to track and analyze the energy deposition within the detector.

Fig. 1. Schematic of the SpaCal model simulated in Geant4.

On top of that, the calorimeter is longitudinally segmented into a front (5 cm) and a back section (10 cm) around the position of the shower maximum of the energy range of interest. A reflector (mirror) is used as a separation between the two sections to allow for a double sided readout [5].

This SpaCal concept is currently investigated by the LHCb collaboration to be used in the inner part of their electromagnetic calorimeter for phase 2 upgrade at High-Luminosity LHC [4] with an interest towards crystal fibers as the active material [3]. The achievable energy and time resolutions [5], in combination with a radiation hard scintillating material could be an interesting option for experiments and detectors at future high-energy colliders.

One of the promising candidates for scintillator material is Gadolinium Gallium Aluminum Garnet ($Gd_3Al_2Ga_3O_{12}$) also known as GAGG, known for its excellent radiation hardness properties [8], high LY, and scintillation characteristics that satisfy all requirements. These attributes make GAGG a promising candidate for high-luminosity environments, partic-

ularly as ongoing research and development aim to optimize its scintillation performance even further [9], [10] and [11].

However, crystal growth technology inherently introduces variability in performance, often due to the distribution coefficients of dopants and co-dopants. In the SpaCal concept, the scintillator will be shaped into long fibers, potentially up to 10 or 15 cm in length, where fluctuations of scintillation properties along the fibers may be anticipated. These fluctuations, driven by dopant distribution, are not expected to be random but may manifest as gradients. This paper focuses on evaluating the impact of such gradients on calorimeter performance, particularly regarding E_R . It aims to define acceptable levels of fluctuation to guide R&D efforts in crystal development and propose optimized crystal arrangements to achieve the best overall performance.

Here, we consider Cz (Czochralski) growth for the crystals, as opposed to micro-pulling down (μ -PD), even though producers are currently using μ -PD primarily to screen the best compositions. Once optimal compositions are identified, R&D efforts will shift towards Cz growth. For Cz growth, we expect only longitudinal variation in scintillation properties, with no radial variation, which is why the latter aspect is not addressed in this study. Additionally, given the $1 \times 1 \text{ mm}^2$ fiber cross-section, the radial variation in scintillation properties could be expected to be negligible if μ -PD growth was considered.

In this paper, we focus on evaluating the impact of the LY gradients along the fibers on the SpaCal calorimeter's performance. Among them we will have a look at the longitudinal variation of LY, denoted as $\Delta_z \text{LY}$, along the fibers. We are specifically interested in determining the extent to which monotonic variations in LY across the fibers impact the detector's overall E_R . For instance, by comparing the performance with different values of $\Delta_z \text{LY}$, one can assess how these variations influence E_R relative to the targeted E_R . This information will help set the specifications for the fiber manufacturers by defining the acceptable limits of this variation and guiding the production requirements.

II. SIMULATION PARAMETERS, TOOLS AND METHODS

A. Light yield and energy resolution

With the context of the SpaCal design established, it is essential to now define two key quantities central to this study: LY and E_R .

LY refers to the intrinsic number of photons that are emitted per unit of energy deposited in a given material. Understanding LY is crucial, as it directly influences the detector's sensitivity to energy deposits, particularly in scintillating materials used in electromagnetic calorimeters.

E_R , is defined by the following equation 1, where \oplus represents a quadratic sum, E the energy, σ_E the standard deviation of the energy and $\langle E \rangle$ the mean value of the energy. The two terms of interest in this expression are the sampling term a and the constant term c , as electronic noise is not considered in this study. Since we are not changing the detector geometry or the fiber dimensions, the sampling term a will stay constant. Thus, our primary focus is on the constant term c for performance comparisons.

$$E_R = \frac{\sigma_E}{\langle E \rangle} = \frac{a}{\sqrt{E}} \oplus \frac{b}{E} \oplus c, \quad \begin{cases} a \propto \text{stochastic fluctuations} \\ b \propto \text{noise contribution} \\ c \propto \text{calorimeter uniformity} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The LHCb ECAL, that will serve as a reference for our upcoming simulation results, which also uses a sampling calorimeter of the Shashlik type, has a constant term value of $c = 1\%$ [6]. By analyzing the constant term under varying LY conditions in our SpaCal model, the objective is to determine the $\Delta_z \text{LY}$ that can be tolerated while maintaining the E_R degradation within acceptable limits.

B. Monte Carlo methods

In that regard, we employed the Hybrid-MC simulation framework, which is built upon the Geant4 toolkit [7]. This framework introduces advanced methods to accelerate the *ray-tracing* of optical photons, and was developed by M. Pizzichemi and L. Martinazzoli for studies concerning the LHCb upgrade II [4].

For the purpose of our simulations, we modeled a W-GAGG SpaCal ($X_0 = 0.62 \text{ cm}$ and $R_M = 1.46 \text{ cm}$), composed of tungsten (W) as the absorber material and GAGG that was chosen for the reason previously given in the Introduction I. The main parameters of the simulated GAGG fibers are given hereafter: $\rho_{\text{GAGG}} = 6.63 \text{ g} \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$, $\text{LY}_{\text{GAGG}} = 30'000$ photons/MeV and $\tau_{\text{eff|GAGG}} \simeq 56.4 \text{ ns}$ which corresponds to the specifications of a standard commercially available GAGG: that was measured in [9]. We do not consider here the recent studies aiming at reducing the time constant to drastically reduce the pile up since the optimization is still ongoing [9]. The geometric and structural properties of the simulated SpaCal are illustrated in Figure 2.

Injection of electrons were simulated into the SpaCal along the z -axis, with a fixed inclination of $\pm 3^\circ$ in both the x and y directions relative to the module axis.

This setup ensures consistency with the experimental configuration used in the results presented in [5] and also allows us to explore the behavior of LY variations under realistic experimental conditions, assessing their impact on the detector's performance.

Fig. 2. Schematic of the geometry of the simulated SpaCal module.

To obtain the E_R , the same method was applied across all subsequent sections. Electrons with energies ranging from 1 to 100 GeV were used, with the specific energy points in the simulations being: 1, 5, 10, 20, 35, 50, and 100 GeV. The corresponding deposited energy in the SpaCal was then computed. This data was fitted using Equation 1, allowing for the extraction of the constant term c , which is of interest.

C. Method for longitudinal variation of LY

To simulate the longitudinal variation in light yield, one can assume a linear dependence along the fiber length (z) for simplicity, as described in Equation 2. This assumption aligns with how such variations are typically measured in garnet-based scintillators, such as GAGG. This is because such inhomogeneities are generated by the coefficient of segregation, leading to an expected monotonic behavior. Additionally, if this coefficient is small, a linear distribution can be considered.

$$\Delta_z LY := a \cdot z + b. \quad (2)$$

The function used for this simulation decreases from the maximum LY to a lower value, which is influenced by the fiber length and the coefficient α , representing the variation in %/cm, as defined in Equation 3:

$$f_{\Delta_z LY}(\alpha, z) \in [1 \mapsto 1 - \alpha \cdot z]. \quad (3)$$

To implement this $\Delta_z LY$ variation, we considered every events, where one event is one electron of a given energy. For each electron, multiple energy depositions (ε_i) occur within the SpaCal, but only those taking place along the fibers are of interest for this study, as they are able to generate electromagnetic showers. Depending on the z position (the z -coordinate of the i -th energy deposit will be denoted as z_i) of these energy depositions, we assign a correction factor based on the value of our function at that specific position: $f_{\Delta_z LY}(\alpha, z_i) = 1 - \alpha \cdot z_i$.

This methodology is illustrated in Figure 3, where the top subplot displays two functions: the blue curve representing $f_{\Delta_z LY}(\alpha = 1\%/cm, z)$ and the green curve for $f_{\Delta_z LY}(\alpha = 5\%/cm, z)$. As shown, the first segment of the SpaCal features 5 cm fibers starting with the highest LY (one of the possibility among the many), while the same trend is observed after the reflector with a new set of fibers that are 10 cm long. On the bottom subplot there is a 2D histogram exhibiting the energy depositions of 5 electrons with an energy of 100 GeV.

The following procedure involves summing all the energy depositions from each event while applying the corresponding correction factor. This yields the collected energy, E_{reco} , as defined in Equation 4, and illustrated in Figure 4, where 1'000 events/ e^- of 35 GeV were simulated, resulting in a distribution of collected energy for each α value.

$$E_{reco} = \sum_i \varepsilon_i \cdot f_{\Delta LY}(z_i) \quad (4)$$

Finally, we repeat this process for a range of electron energies and various values of α , and then compare the resulting constant terms to determine which configuration provides a value as close as possible to 1%.

Fig. 3. 2D histogram of energy depositions for 5 electrons with $E = 100$ GeV with corresponding longitudinal variation of LY of the modeled SpaCal.

Fig. 4. Distribution of energy depositions for a 1'000 electrons with $E = 35$ GeV for various α .

D. Optimal configuration of the SpaCal fibers

Having established a method to compare different values of longitudinal LY variation, the next step is to explore the optimal assembly of fibers in the SpaCal. The goal is to determine whether it is preferable to use two sets of prefabricated fibers—one set of 5 cm fibers and another set of 10 cm fibers—or to use a single set of 15 cm fibers that can be cut into 5 cm and 10 cm segments. In both cases, the fibers need to be split due to the requirement of placing a reflector between the two sections of the SpaCal. A total length of 15 cm is considered realistic given the desired attenuation length of the SpaCal. As part of the analysis, it will be evaluated whether positioning the highest LY end or the lowest LY end (head or tail of fibers from Cz growth) is more effective, as well as whether positioning the fiber's front or back end (before and after the reflector) is more advantageous in both sections of the SpaCal.

This study was possible due to the flexibility of the SpaCal, which allows us to explore and compare various configurations of fiber arrangement.

All simulated configurations are illustrated in Figure 5, for all of them we once again plotted, as a representative case,

the $f_{\Delta_z LY}(\alpha = 1\%/cm, z)$ (blue) and $f_{\Delta_z LY}(\alpha = 5\%/cm, z)$ (green) functions.

Fig. 5. Illustration of the configurations for the fibers arrangement simulated in the SpaCal. C stands for Configurations and $f_{\Delta_z LY}(\alpha = 1\%/cm, z)$ is represented by the blue curves while $f_{\Delta_z LY}(\alpha = 5\%/cm, z)$ is represented by the green ones.

For each of the configuration we followed the same procedure as before by just using a different function for the correction factor that will be applied to the energy deposits.

E. Normal distribution of variation of LY

Knowing that scintillator producers will face a huge production of fiber, one has to anticipate fluctuations from fiber to fiber. Hence this paper also aimed to investigate the effects of those fluctuations, in addition to the longitudinal variation of LY that may also fluctuate among the fibers. To achieve this, a new quantity, β , defined in the equation 6, was introduced to represent the maximum LY values for each fiber.

The distribution of α is defined in Equation 5, μ represents the mean value of maximum LY among the fibers while σ is the jitter from fiber to fiber around μ . The distribution is centered around 1.1%/cm and spans from 0 to 2%/cm. This range reflects the limits we consider to be acceptable, to avoid degrading the performance of the SpaCal, as discussed in the subsequent section (III). The distribution is modeled as a truncated normal distribution, ensuring that the values remain within the allowable limits:

$$\alpha \sim \mathcal{N}_{[0,2]}(\mu = 1.10, \sigma^2 = 0.25^2). \quad (5)$$

The symbol \sim indicates that our quantity follows a random distribution, specifically a normal distribution (\mathcal{N}).

The choice of a normal distribution is justified by the Central Limit Theorem, which suggests that the sum of a large number of independent random variables tends to be normally distributed, regardless of the original distribution of the variables. This aligns with the expectation that small, random fluctuations in production parameters—such as material composition, temperature, and processing conditions when

growing the fibers—can lead to variations in LY that are symmetrically distributed around a mean value. By representing these variations with a normal distribution, we can accurately simulate the potential discrepancies in LY that may arise during the growth of the scintillating fibers.

Unlike the fixed α distribution, the β values will remain unconstrained. Instead, different standard deviations (σ) around the mean value $\mu = 1.0$ will be reproduced, as illustrated in Equation 6.

$$\beta \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu = 1.0, \sigma^2), \quad (6)$$

$$\text{where } \sigma^2 = [0.01^2, 0.05^2, 0.10^2, 0.15^2, 0.20^2] \quad (7)$$

The idea behind this approach is to assess the impact of increasingly larger variations around a nominal LY value ($\mu = 1$), such as 1% ($\sigma^2 = 0.01^2$) or even up to 20% ($\sigma^2 = 0.20^2$), an illustration of the random distribution of those values in the fibers of the modeled SpaCal can be seen on the Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Illustration of the variation of maximal value of LY ($\beta \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu = 1.0, \sigma^2 = 0.15^2)$) of the fibers in the (x, y) plane of the SpaCal. The colormap ranges from 0%/cm (blue) to 2%/cm (red).

Ultimately, the function used as a correction factor for the LY along the z axis of the fibers will be distributed as: $[\beta \mapsto \beta - \alpha]$, instead of $[1 \mapsto 1 - \alpha]$, as it was done [for the longitudinal variation of LY in section II-C].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Optimal configuration of the SpaCal fibers

For all subsequent subsections, the sampling parameter a was set to 9.54% based on its value obtained when fitting the E_R of the SpaCal in the ideal case (where $\alpha = 0\%$ per cm: no variation in LY is assumed). This allowed for a clearer comparison of the constant term c . The noise term b was excluded from these simulations. Consequently, c is the only free parameter, as it is influenced by the development of the shower within the SpaCal, which depends on the variation in light yield $\Delta_z LY$.

The obtained results can be seen in the Figure 7, where the constant term is plotted against the $\Delta_z LY$ for the five different configurations, as defined in Figure 5. What we notice

TABLE I
E_R PARAMETERS FOR THE DIFFERENT CONFIGURATIONS

E _R parameters	α [% / cm]	0 (ideal)	1	2	3	4	5	6
	a [%]		9.54 ± 0.02	9.53 ± 0.03	9.53 ± 0.02	9.53 ± 0.02	9.54 ± 0.02	9.54 ± 0.03
Segmented fibers - Config. 1	c [%]	1.23 ± 0.08	1.22 ± 0.09	1.24 ± 0.09	1.27 ± 0.09	1.34 ± 0.09	1.42 ± 0.09	1.51 ± 0.10
Segmented fibers - Config. 2	c [%]	1.23 ± 0.08	1.14 ± 0.07	1.24 ± 0.09	1.49 ± 0.10	1.96 ± 0.12	2.61 ± 0.12	3.43 ± 0.13
Segmented fibers - Config. 3	c [%]	1.23 ± 0.08	1.15 ± 0.08	1.14 ± 0.08	1.20 ± 0.08	1.32 ± 0.09	1.65 ± 0.10	1.64 ± 0.10
Single fibers - Config. 4	c [%]	1.23 ± 0.08	1.21 ± 0.08	1.56 ± 0.11	2.27 ± 0.13	3.22 ± 0.13	4.31 ± 0.14	5.67 ± 0.18
Segmented fibers - Config. 5	c [%]	1.23 ± 0.08	1.21 ± 0.08	1.32 ± 0.10	1.54 ± 0.11	1.96 ± 0.12	2.55 ± 0.12	3.37 ± 0.13

is that using segmented fibers instead of one single fiber (configuration 4), greatly helps mitigating the worsening of the E_R.

is supported by our simulation results, particularly in the regions where the electromagnetic shower develops.

Fig. 7. Evolution of the constant term for various α for the 5 configurations of fibers in the SpaCal.

To compare the performance of various configurations involving segmented fibers, the general strategy is to identify which configuration yields the lowest value of the constant term c . When examining LY variation values ranging from 0%/cm to 4%/cm (twice the acceptable limit, as discussed later in Section III-B), configuration n°3 consistently provides the best performance. This can be explained by the fact that the shower maximum is located around the reflector for the energies we consider, as shown in Figure 8. This point coincides with where the reflector is, between the two fiber segments. The barycenter of the energy deposition for the three spatial coordinates (x_g, y_g, z_g) can be computed using equation 8, where N represents the number of energy deposits, and ε_i are the values of those deposits.

$$j_g := \frac{1}{E_{\text{tot}}} \cdot \sum_i^N j_i \cdot \varepsilon_i, \text{ where } j_g \in \{x_g, y_g, z_g\}. \quad (8)$$

Therefore, it is most logical to place the part of the fiber with the highest LY near the reflector, in both section, as the LY decreases from head to tail along the fiber. This configuration

B. Longitudinal variation of LY

Larger variations in LY led to a decreased energy collection capability of the SpaCal, as illustrated in Figure 4. Fitting the energy distributions across the entire electron energy range, for all α values and different configurations, yielded the results presented in Table I. This table indicates that when utilizing the *optimal* configuration (designated as configuration number 3), it is crucial to keep longitudinal LY variations below 2% per cm to minimize the impact on the detector's performance. Note that the uncertainties provided are statistical and arise from the fitting procedure (1σ error). Systematic uncertainties are not included in this case.

C. Normal distribution of variation of LY

In the final part of this study, the β distribution was implemented, also using the *optimal* configuration and the expected α distribution that manufacturers should aim to achieve, defined as $\alpha \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu = 1.1, \sigma^2 = 0.25^2)$.

The results obtained are presented in Table II, where the constant term c for various distributions can be found. It is shown that to achieve a term close to that of the current Shashlik ECAL of LHCb [6], the variations of LY between fibers should remain below 1% ($\sigma^2 = 0.01^2$).

TABLE II
CONSTANT TERM FOR VARIOUS DISTRIBUTION OF β WHEN USING THE 3rd CONFIGURATION AND $\alpha \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu = 1.1, \sigma^2 = 0.25^2)$.

β distribution	c term [%]
$\beta \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu = 1.0, \sigma^2 = 0.01^2)$	1.18 ± 0.09
$\beta \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu = 1.0, \sigma^2 = 0.05^2)$	1.33 ± 0.07
$\beta \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu = 1.0, \sigma^2 = 0.10^2)$	1.76 ± 0.07
$\beta \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu = 1.0, \sigma^2 = 0.15^2)$	2.29 ± 0.09
$\beta \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu = 1.0, \sigma^2 = 0.20^2)$	2.61 ± 0.09

IV. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

The simulations performed in section III demonstrate that using segmented fibers in the SpaCal offers significant benefits in terms of E_R compared to single fibers. This improvement

Fig. 8. *Left*: 3D plot of barycenter positions (x_g, y_g, z_g) of 1'000 electrons ranging from 1 to 100 GeV with SpaCal absorber in black and reflector in green. *Right*: Histogram of barycenter z position (z_g) of 1'000 electrons (projection of the left plot on z axis).

can be further enhanced by employing a specific assembly method for the fibers in this sampling calorimeter (configuration 3). Furthermore, to mitigate the possible degradation of detector performance due to longitudinal variation of LY, it is required to keep the latter below the 2%/cm threshold. Our simulation also highlights that the variation of LY from fiber to fiber (σ) should be kept below 1% whenever possible.

These simulated results will be evaluated in testbeam facilities such as CERN SPS or DESY, where the performance of the detector will be assessed with real particle interactions. If the simulated outcomes are validated through experimental measurements, they will then serve as specifications for the fiber producers.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was carried out in the framework of the Crystal Clear Collaboration and received support by CERN EP-R&D and the Twinning European project (TWISMA, grant agreement n°101078960). The authors would like to extend their gratitude to their colleagues from the LHCb ECAL Upgrade II (PicoCal) group for the fruitful discussions.

All authors declare that they have no known conflicts of interest in terms of competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have an influence or are relevant to the work reported in this paper.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Kholodenko, "LHCb ECAL upgrade II," PoS, vol. PANIC2021, p. 100, 2022, doi: 10.22323/1.380.0100.
- [2] R. Wigmans, "Recent results from the spaghetti calorimeter project," *Nucl. Instrum. Methods Phys. Res. A*, vol. 315, no. 1, pp. 299–310, 1992, doi: 10.1016/0168-9002(92)90719-K.
- [3] L. Martinazzoli, "Crystal Fibers for the LHCb Calorimeter Upgrade," IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci., vol. 67, no. 6, p. 1003, 2020, doi: 10.1109/TNS.2020.2975570.
- [4] LHCb collaboration, "Framework TDR for the LHCb Upgrade II: Opportunities in flavour physics, and beyond, in the HL-LHC era," CERN, Geneva, techreport, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2776420>

- [5] L. An et al., "Performance of a spaghetti calorimeter prototype with tungsten absorber and garnet crystal fibres," Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment, vol. 1045, p. 167629, 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2022.167629>.
- [6] S. Barsuk, "The Shashlik Electro-Magnetic Calorimeter for the LHCb Experiment," CERN, Geneva, techreport, 2004. [Online]. Available: <https://cds.cern.ch/record/1485500>
- [7] S. Agostinelli et al., "Geant4—a simulation toolkit," Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment, vol. 506, no. 3, pp. 250–303, 2003, doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-9002\(03\)01368-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-9002(03)01368-8).
- [8] M. T. Lucchini et al., "Effect of Mg²⁺ ions co-doping on timing performance and radiation tolerance of Cerium doped Gd₃Al₂Ga₃O₁₂ crystals," Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment, vol. 816, pp. 176–183, 2016, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2016.02.004>.
- [9] L. Martinazzoli, N. Kratochwil, S. Gundacker, and E. Auffray, "Scintillation properties and timing performance of state-of-the-art Gd₃Al₂Ga₃O₁₂ single crystals," Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment, vol. 1000, p. 165231, 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2021.165231>.
- [10] C. Dujardin et al., "Needs, Trends, and Advances in Inorganic Scintillators," in IEEE Transactions on Nuclear Science, vol. 65, no. 8, pp. 1977–1997, Aug. 2018, doi: 10.1109/TNS.2018.2840160. keywords: Scintillators;Crystals;Detectors;Energy resolution;National security;High energy physics;Fast timing;high energy physics (HEP);homeland security;inorganic scintillator;medical imaging;scintillation.
- [11] L. Martinazzoli et al., "Compositional engineering of multicomponent garnet scintillators: towards an ultra-accelerated scintillation response," Mater. Adv., vol. 3, no. 17, pp. 6842–6852, 2022, doi: 10.1039/D2MA00626J.